

Integrating Indigenous Knowledge and Formal Education: A Study of Community Based Schooling in Arunachal Pradesh

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Abstract

Now a days community based schools are emerging as vital spaces where formal education and indigenous culture are nurtured together. In far flung Menjwk Meqkok Rwggu in Basar, Lepa Rada District, Arunachal Pradesh reflects this blend as it integrates the NCERT curriculum with native language, cultural practices and traditional knowledge system for Galo Community children. it aligns with NEP-2020 which emphasises that school should ensure "Indian Knowledge Systems. Including tribal knowledge and indigenous and traditional ways of learning. will be covered and included in the curriculum, pedagogy of our institutions wherever relevant." (NEP-2020, para 4.27). This paper examines the institutional role of such schools in serving tribal communities and weighs their perceived impact on students are the wider local society. Guided by the objectives of understanding educational purpose, community influence the future needs. the present study draws upon an interview with the school principal who provided in-depth insights into school's philosophy and practice. this integration is perceived by the principal as enriching student's motivation enhancing community pride and strengthening inter-generation transmission of language and tradition.

this paper highlights about community based tribal schools not only educate but also heal cultural disconnections. in the context, such models can inspire more inclusive and culturally resonant educational practices across indigenous context.

Keywords

Menjwk Meqkok Rwggu, Indigenous Knowledge System, Galo Community, Modern Education.

Introduction

Background of Menjwk Meqkok Rwggu

Menjwk Meqkok Rwggu is a Gurukul style School located in Basar, Leparada district of Arunachal Pradesh. It was set up in 2022 by the Donyi Polo Cultural & Charitable Trust (DPCCT) with the aim of preserving tribal culture while providing formal education to local children. The school follows the NCERT curriculum but places emphasis on indigenous culture, language, sports, crafts and traditions of the Galo tribe. Classes range from grade I to IV With around 47-100 students enrolled (all from Galo community) with the fee structure which is 5000 in a year.

The approach adopted by Menjwk Meqkok Rwggu serves as a model for culturally responsive education, where the transmission of indigenous knowledge and values is considered as vital as conventional schooling. This dual focus keeps children with the tools to navigate future challenges while nurturing respect and pride for their heritage. Consequently, the school not only prepares students to drive in an increasingly global society but also contributes to the continuity of revitalisation of the Galo community's unique cultural legacy. The institution fosters a strong sense of identity and belonging among students ensuring that their cultural roots remain vibrant and relevant in their personal and academic growth.

Objective of study

The researcher formulated objectives qualitatively on the basis of the research problem in order to gain an in-depth understanding.

1. Explore the institutional educational role of community based school serving tribal communities.
2. Understand the perceived impact of MMR school on students and local communities.
3. Identify key challenges and future needs of community based school in the contest of Arunachal Pradesh.

Review of Literature

India is home to many tribal communities with rich cultural traditions. In remote regions modern education often fails to connect with local culture and values. In response to this challenges Community based schools have emerged that combine formal education with indigenous knowledge and practices (Amit, 2024). It has been studied that embedding native language instruction alongside the NCERT curriculum enhance comprehension and cognitive engagement (Kartini et. Al.,2025, Zang, 2023).

Language is a critical medium for learning delivering content in a familiar tongue helps bridge gaps caused by linguistic alienation in mainstream education thereby fostering better academic participation. Further incorporating traditional cultural practices and indigenous knowledge systems affirm students' identities and nurtures a sense of belonging within the school environment. This identity affirmation can increase motivation and engagement, reducing dropout rates often linked to cultural dissonance in formal schooling. (Abdalla & Moussa, 2024) nowadays community based schools are emerging as vital spaces where formal education and generous culture are nurture together community base schools serve as vital platforms where elders and cultural custodians actively participate in curriculum development and School activities. Their involvement ensures authenticity and relevance of the content while simultaneously strengthening community ownership of education, which is crucial for sustainability and acceptance addressing socio-economic challenges is indispensable (Ramya, 2013). Limited access to resources and economic hardship often hinder consistent goal, attendance and learning outcomes. Community based education models need to integrate support mechanism such as flexible schedules, local resources, mobilisation and culturally sensitive paragraph to mitigate these barriers aligning these initiatives with NEP 2020 directives on Indian knowledge systems reinforces policy relevance. The study can inform the design of culturally responses of curricula and pedagogy is that are scalable across other tribal regions, thus contributing to broader educational equity goals. (Vaithianathan, 2025, Raj, 2024)

In far flung Menjwk Meqkok Rwggu in Basar. Arunachal Pradesh reflects this blend as it integrates the NCERT curriculum with native language, cultural practises and traditional knowledge system of Golo community children. It aligns with NEP 2020 which emphasises that schools should ensure "Indian knowledge system including tribal knowledge and indigenous and traditional ways of learning will be covered and included in the curriculum of our institutions wherever relevant." (NEP-2020, para 4.27). (Ramya, 2013) highlights issues of socio-economic backwardness and Limited access to formal Education, which create a disconnect between indigenous knowledge system and modern schooling. Despite its rich cultural analysis the study leaves a research gap in terms of systematically examining how these cultural elements directly affect students participation, academic performance and engage engagement within formal education systems which is essential for developing culturally responsive pedagogical practices.

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative approach to explore the role and functioning of a community based school. The data was collected from the school principal Mr. Goto Bam of a selected school Menjwk Meqkok Rwggu located in Basar town, Leparada District, Arunachal Pradesh. A purposive sampling technique was used to select the participant. The primary data was gathered through an interview using a semi-structured interview schedule. This allowed the participant to share detailed information and experiences. The collected data was analyzed using a thematic analysis to identify key patterns and insights related to the objectives of the study.

Result and Discussion**Institutional Setup and Role of the School**

Blending modern and cultural education the Institute Menjwk Meqkok Rwggu integrates the preservation and promotion of the indigenous Galo culture with modern academic learning. It aims to impart the Galo culture identity by teaching traditional knowledge, language, rituals, prayers, medicinal plants, crafts and indigenous games alongside subjects like English, Hindi and science as per NCERT requirements from one generation to another. This dual focus ensure that students not only gain modern education essential for broad society engagement but also develop a strong connection of their heritage.

The school follows the ancient Gurukul concept (NEP 2020), emphasising cultural immersion and holistic learning. It emphasises the instruction and cultural practises in local dialect/language with a language development commit supporting this effort. Further incorporating a specific language themed session in their daily curriculum. Written and verbal learning are conducted in that one hour period in the weekdays. Learning of chanting, rituals, traditional crafts and ancient Galo games are learnt on Sunday. The level of difficulty increases according to the class level.

The institution encourages participation in literary competition. Where students have exceeded in language translation and sports, within the four (4) year span of the Institute the student has brought various accolades to the Institute board in District and state level competitions, demonstrating the balance between tradition and contemporary skills. Also proving their proficiency in modern education with acceptance to their cultural roots. Further the curriculum incorporates local sports like Daddi Leko on line with global and national sports. Learning discussion and production of local artistry techniques like Oppo, Iggin, Bolup etc constitutes the daily routine of the students.

Over all the Institute cultivate the younger generations' cultural roots while equipping them with modern education. Ensuring the survival and evaluation of the Galo indigenous identity in a changing world.

Understanding the Perceived Impact

Since the inception of this Institute by Donyi Polo Cultural & Charitable Trust (DPCCT) with reference to Menjwk Meqkok Rwggu (MMR) school has a significant perceived impact on both students and the local community by integrating indigenous knowledge with formal education. This blended approach promotes holistic development, moral education and confidence to accept their roots to the global culture, reciprocating the principle of NCF 2005 that students should be able to incorporate their education in practical world. Involvement of SMC members, community, volunteer teachers prove a strong sense of belonging and accountability among the students as a whole. Moreover, further reducing the disparity in literacy rate among the population and connecting to the remote corner of the state.

Challenges

The review of education policy in recent years (NEP 2020), comprehension and incorporation of traditional knowledge in school education has given inception of such Gurukul. This novel and fresh design collides with the age old ongoing form of Education, creating board resistance and hurdle for emination of such institutes. The Menjwk Meqkok Rwggu (MMR) School faces several challenges that affect its overall functioning and long term sustainability. One of the major challenges is the lack of adequate funding as the institution largely depends on donation, community contributions and support system such as auto debit arrangements. The use of traditional bamboo structures, though culturally meaningful raises concerns about durability and safety among parents. Moreover, with rapid globalisation and competition among the peers regarding the scope and competition between modern knowledge and cultural views the perception gap regarding the quality of Education. As a result many financially stable families opt for private schools over the Gurukul Based system. This creates an enrolment challenge as some parents equate Modern facilities with better education. The school also faces issues related to Limited inclusivity as divisions exist among people of different believes within the community. There is also common misconception that culture and religion are the same, which leads to the hesitation of reluctance among some families to send their children to the school. This prejudice creates a barrier to wider participation as certain groups perceive the institution as being aligned with only specific religious believes such as Donyi Polo rather than as a space for cultural and educational learning. As a result, the school's objective of promoting indigenous culture in an inclusive manner is sometimes misunderstood, affecting enrolment and community acceptance, which may restrict diversity and why their acceptance. Furthermore, being a relatively new institution it is still in the process of establishing academic credibility and expanding its outreach.

Conclusion

Community based schools like Menjwk Meqkok Rwggu (MMR) are important for tribal communities. They help students receive formal education while maintaining a strong connection to their culture and traditions. Such schools demonstrate the learning does not need to be separate from heritage. However, support infrastructure and awareness are needed to sustain and expand these efforts.

The study highlights then when education respects cultural identity and modern knowledge together it becomes more meaningful for students and communities.

Suggestions for the future Study

Based on the overview and document study the following recommendation can strengthen the school's role:

1. Stable funding sources: long-term financial planning involving government supports, NGO and community partnership.
2. Infrastructure development: better classrooms, libraries and facilities that match educational needs while preserving traditional design.

3. Teacher training: workshop on train teachers in both modern pedagogy and indigenous teaching methods.
4. Community awareness programs: encouraging parents to understand the value of blended cultural education.

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